

THE INFLUENCE OF PARENTS' PERSONAL AND SOCIETAL VALUES ON ADOLESCENTS' VALUES

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ABSTRACT

Parents are considered the primary socializers of their adolescent children, striving to model appropriate personal values and acceptable societal values for them to stay morally upright members of society. This study was conceptualized to examine if parents' personal values and societal values influence their adolescents' values. This study is anchored on Schwartz's Theory of Basic Human Values (2012) and Bronfenbrenner's Ecological System Theory (1979). To achieve the purpose of the study, the Portrait Value Questionnaire, an instrument developed by Schwartz, et al., (2001) was utilized to one hundred twenty (120) participants. The participants were eighty (80) parents consisted of forty (40) mothers and forty (40) fathers and forty (40) grade six students in one of the public schools in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City. Descriptive correlational design was employed. Frequency, mean, percentage, and standard deviation was used to determine the parents' personal values and societal values and the adolescents' values. Multiple regression was also utilized to find if the parents' personal values and societal values predict their adolescents' values. The findings of the study showed that both parents demonstrated high level of personal values that substantially influence their adolescents who highly manifest their values while only the mother's societal values highly influence their adolescents' values. Parents must continue to inculcate and model the same appropriate personal and acceptable societal values to their adolescents.

Key Words: *Parents' personal values, Parents' societal values, Adolescents' values*

INTRODUCTION

Parents always consider their adolescents as gifts and blessings. Hence, they play a key role in their holistic development, including the values that adolescents ought to develop. Therefore, it is a moral responsibility of parents to instill moral values in their adolescents as early as possible for them to be productive members of society.

Moreover, parents' values transmission is a pivotal process in the development of an individual and an essential aim of socialization (Kelly et al. 2022; Barni & Ranieri, 2023). They are abstract desires applicable in all circumstances; values are used to judge people and communities, to discover changes in society over time, and to expound the motivational basis of attitudes and behaviors (Schwartz, 2022; Assor et al. 2020).

The acquisition of social competencies throughout adolescents' lives is acquired in the family, the primary source for values transmission (Ezekiel & Ayo, 2024). Parents are considered the fundamental agents of societies in the never-ending struggle to transmit traditions to adolescents (Brenoe & Epper, 2022; Barni et al. 2023). Basically, transmission was considered an intergenerational values reproduction (Pustulka, 2023; Tulviste, 2020). In the past decades, psychological research has made considerable progress toward recognizing the complex nature of values transmission across generations (Barni et al. 2023). Transmission is considered an interdependent way in which fathers, mothers, and adolescents are considered to have innate capabilities in building positive social interactions with one another (Jain, 2023). Intergenerational differences are the results of the choices that parents make concerning what values they will pass on and from adolescents' decisions to accept or disregard them (Williamson, 2024). Societal values are the values parents wish their adolescents to uphold (Elsayed, 2024). Parents are aware of the importance of distinguishing between what is beneficial for themselves and what may be appropriate for their adolescents (Higgins, 2023; Benish-Weisman et al. 2021). This suggests that parents modify their societal values to enable themselves to fit with what they consider favorable for their adolescents (Rachmayani & Zabrina, 2023).

Basically, this is important for parents to equip their adolescents with the necessary values needed in a broader social life (LaMonica, 2024). In fact, the adolescent stage is the time of identity development, where the desire for autonomy and adherence to family and societal standards co-exist, with the latter viewed as necessary for upholding acceptable behavior (Bogaerts et al. 2021; Schwartz, 2022). Naturally, there are other socialization influences (e.g., horizontal transmission between members of the same generation, like peers) as well as genetic and environmental influences on adolescents' value development (Macdonald & Howard, 2020).

Furthermore, research on adolescence has continuously emphasized the complexity of their values development (Edwards & Kirven, 2020). It is during this stage of development that adolescents are increasingly aware of tolerant or discriminating social norms, adapting their responses and attitudes accordingly (Lewis-Smith et al. 2020). Indeed, adolescents must possess appropriate personal values and acceptable

societal values that will lead them to foster positive social interactions in all circumstances rather than becoming delinquent (Laurson & Veenstra, 2021). The rising concern for adolescent offenders is a great concern for values formation (Gogua, 2020). Moral decay has affected Philippine society (Macaraeg, 2020). Juvenile delinquency has become a terrifying reality (Darvishi et al. 2022).

School is the vital partner of the home to patiently guide and redirect adolescents on how to become morally upright members of society in any instance (Li, 2021). Educators, as the main socializers in an educational institution, must uphold appropriate personal values and acceptable societal values that will positively influence the formation of adolescents' values (Auer et al. 2023). Maintaining good communication and working together with parents are matters educators also need to establish to guide the development of adolescents' values (Haj & David, 2024). Through these, educators will have a conscientious understanding of the situations and adolescents' families may be experiencing, involving economic and social factors that are influential on their values formation (Pavitola et al. 2024). Hence, modeling a positive value system is a responsibility of every educator aside from navigating the academic world flawlessly (Chichekian, 2023).

Since parents' values serve as a guiding force in children's lives, shaping their character, beliefs, and behaviors from early childhood into adulthood, the researcher was motivated to study the personal and societal values that parents uphold if it has influenced adolescents' values.

Research Questions

This study intends to determine if parents' personal and societal values influence their adolescents' personal and societal values. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the father-participants assessment their values in terms of:
 - 1.1 Personal Values
 - 1.1.1 Self-enhancement; and
 - 1.1.2 Openness to change
 - 1.2 Societal Values
 - 1.2.1 Self-transcendence; and
 - 1.2.2 Conservation?
2. What is the mother-participants assessment their values in terms of:
 - 2.1. Personal Values
 - 2.1.1 Self-enhancement; and
 - 2.1.2 Openness to change
 - 2.2. Societal Values
 - 2.2.1. Self-transcendence; and
 - 2.2.2. Conservation?
3. What is the adolescent-participants assessment their values in terms of:

- 3.1 Personal Values
 - 3.1.1. Self-enhancement; and
 - 3.1.2. Openness to change
 - 3.2 Societal Values
 - 3.2.1. Self-transcendence; and
 - 3.2.2. Conservation?
 - 4. Do the parents' personal and societal values significantly influence adolescents' values?
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METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design to determine whether the parents' personal values and societal values influence their adolescents. A total of eighty (80) parent-participants consisting of forty (40) mothers, forty (40) fathers, and forty (40) grade six students from one of the public schools in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines. The instrument for the data collection was a modified questionnaire based on the Portrait Values Questionnaire developed by Schwartz, et al., (2001), measuring personal values and societal values. The questionnaire was composed of thirty-five (35) descriptions of Personal values which were categorized as self-enhancement (achievement and power) and openness to change (hedonism, stimulation, and self-direction), and thirty-five (33) descriptions of societal values which were categorized as self-transcendence (universality and benevolence) and conservation (security, tradition, and conformity). Each sub-values were composed of 6 or 7 verbal portraits describing a person's goals, wishes or aspirations that point implicitly to the importance of one value dimension for Problems 1, 2 and 3. The instrument was subjected to content validation by the members of the panel and experts in the field. Then, pilot testing was done to twenty (20) fathers, 20 mothers and 20 adolescents who were excluded as the research participants. Cronbach alpha coefficient was used to determine its reliability. Problems 1, 2 and 3 employed descriptive statistics in terms of frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation to describe the variables. For Problem 4, regression analysis was employed to determine if the parents' values significantly influence the adolescents' values.

RESULTS

The fathers displayed high levels of both personal and societal values. They emphasized self-enhancement and openness to change as personal values, while prioritizing self-transcendence and conservation as societal values. This balanced approach suggests that fathers aim to guide their adolescents through the challenges of growing up, fostering a strong sense of self, social responsibility, and cultural identity.

The mothers exhibited moderate levels of personal values in terms of self-enhancement and high levels of openness to change. They also demonstrated high societal values, emphasizing self-transcendence and conservation. This implies that mothers seek to nurture their adolescents' emotional intelligence, critical thinking skills, and ability to form healthy relationships, which are essential for their long-term success and well-being.

The adolescents showed moderate levels of personal values in terms of self-enhancement and high levels of openness to change. They also displayed high societal values, focusing on self-transcendence and conservation. This suggests that adolescents are developing a balanced set of values that will guide their personal growth and social interactions.

The study found that both mothers' personal values (self-enhancement and openness to change) and societal values (self-transcendence and conservation) were significant predictors of their adolescents' corresponding values. However, only the fathers' personal values (self-enhancement and openness to change) had a significant influence on their adolescents' personal values. This highlights the unique roles that mothers and fathers play in shaping their children's value systems, with mothers having a more comprehensive impact on both personal and societal values, while fathers' influence is more focused on personal values.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents a summary of the fathers', mothers' and adolescents' personal and societal values. First, the overall mean of 4.10 suggests that fathers in this study possess high levels of both personal and societal values. When examining the specific values, the data reveals that the fathers' societal value of conservation (M=4.37) obtained the highest mean. This finding implies that fathers place great emphasis on the importance of securing themselves and their families, establishing harmonious relationships, and respecting the customs of their culture and religion.

Table 1.
Summary Table of the Fathers', Mothers' and Adolescents' Personal and Societal Values

Participants	Values	Specific Value	Mean	Interpretation
Fathers' Values	Personal	Self-Enhancement	3.59	High
		Openness to Change	4.09	High
	Societal	Self-Transcendence	4.36	High
		Conservation	4.37	High

		<i>Overall Mean</i>	4.10	High
Mothers' Values	Personal	Self-Enhancement	3.46	Moderate
		Openness to Change	4.04	High
	Societal	Self-Transcendence	4.37	High
		Conservation	4.10	High
		<i>Overall Mean</i>	3.99	High
Adolescents' Values	Personal	Self-Enhancement	3.45	Moderate
		Openness to Change	4.05	High
	Societal	Self-Transcendence	4.24	High
		Conservation	4.21	High
		<i>Overall Mean</i>	3.99	High

Conversely, the figures revealed that the fathers' personal value of self-enhancement (M=3.59) received the lowest mean. However, it is important to note that despite being the lowest among the values assessed, the mean of 3.59 still indicates a high level of importance placed on this value. This suggests that fathers highly stress the significance of demonstrating competence according to social standards and maintaining a good public image and social recognition.

The high overall mean of the fathers' personal and societal values has significant implications for their parenting style and the development of their adolescent children (Lal, 2023). By placing a strong emphasis on both personal and societal values, fathers can create a well-rounded and balanced approach to guiding their adolescents through the challenges of growing up (Goldsmith, 2023). The high level of conservation values indicates that fathers prioritize the safety, security, and well-being of their families, which can provide a stable and nurturing environment for their adolescents to thrive (Merrick et al. 2020). Additionally, by emphasizing the importance of harmonious relationships and respect for cultural and religious customs, fathers can help their adolescents develop a strong sense of identity, belonging, and social responsibility (Allen, 2023).

While the personal value of self-enhancement received the lowest mean, its high score still underscores the importance fathers place on personal achievement and social recognition (BusuMallick, 2021). This suggests that fathers aim to strike a balance between promoting individual success and maintaining a strong sense of social connectedness (Clark et al. 2021). By modeling this balance, fathers can encourage their adolescents to strive for personal excellence while also remaining grounded in their social and cultural context (Shitole, 2020).

In summary, the high levels of personal and societal values exhibited by fathers in this study highlight the multifaceted nature of their parenting approach. By prioritizing conservation, self-transcendence, openness to change, and self-enhancement, fathers demonstrate a commitment to fostering the overall well-being and development of their

adolescents (Hongell et al. 2023). This balanced approach can help adolescents navigate the challenges of growing up while developing a strong sense of self, social responsibility, and cultural identity (Longchar, 2024). As role models, fathers who embody these values can have a profound impact on the personal and social development of their adolescent children (Yousefi, 2023).

Second, the mothers' personal and societal values overall mean of 3.99 suggests that mothers in this study possess high levels of both personal and societal values. When examining the specific values, the data reveal that the mothers' societal value of self-transcendence (M=4.37) obtained the highest mean. This finding indicates that mothers place great emphasis on the importance of sustaining and developing the well-being of those they regularly interact with, as well as others and the preservation of nature. Conversely, the figures show that the mothers' personal value of self-enhancement (M=3.46) received the lowest mean. This suggests that mothers place moderate emphasis on the importance of being ambitious, successful, capable, and influential to survive and achieve their objectives.

The high overall mean of the mothers' personal and societal values has significant implications for their parenting approach and the development of their adolescent children. By placing a strong emphasis on both personal and societal values, mothers can create a well-rounded and balanced environment that nurtures their adolescents' growth and well-being (Maurer, 2023). The high level of self-transcendence values indicates that mothers prioritize the welfare of others and the environment, which can foster a sense of empathy, social responsibility, and ecological awareness in their adolescents (Straupaite, 2023).

While the personal value of self-enhancement received the lowest mean, it is important to note that a moderate emphasis on ambition, success, capability, and influence can still be beneficial for adolescents' personal development (Hirschi & Spurk, 2021). Mothers who encourage their adolescents to strive for achievement and cultivate their skills and abilities can help them build self-confidence, resilience, and a strong work ethic (Arora & Kishor, 2020). However, the lower emphasis on self-enhancement compared to other values suggests that mothers may also prioritize other aspects of personal growth, such as self-acceptance, emotional well-being, and positive relationships (Chitoroga, 2022).

The balance between personal and societal values demonstrated by mothers in this study can have a profound impact on the overall development of their adolescent children. By modeling a commitment to both individual growth and social responsibility, mothers can help their adolescents navigate the challenges of adolescence while developing a strong sense of self and a deep connection to the world around them (Kebria et al. 2021). This balanced approach can foster adolescents' emotional intelligence, critical thinking skills, and ability to form healthy relationships, all of which are crucial for their long-term success and well-being.

Overall, the high levels of personal and societal values exhibited by mothers in this study highlight the multifaceted nature of their parenting approach (Noonan, 2024; Ajayi, 2023). By prioritizing self-transcendence, openness to change, and conservation, while also placing moderate emphasis on self-enhancement, mothers demonstrate a commitment to fostering the overall well-being and development of their adolescents (Ben-Arieh et al. 2020). This balanced approach can help adolescents grow into well-rounded, socially responsible, and emotionally resilient individuals who are equipped to thrive in an increasingly complex world (Rathee, 2023).

Third, the overall mean of 3.99 suggests that adolescents in this study possess high levels of both personal and societal values. When examining the specific values, the data reveals that the adolescents' societal value of self-transcendence ($M=4.24$) obtained the highest mean. This finding indicates that adolescents place great emphasis on ensuring the welfare of people within their group, the larger society and world, and the environment. Conversely, the figures show that the adolescents' personal value of self-enhancement ($M=3.45$) received the lowest mean. This implies that adolescents place moderate emphasis on the importance of authority, wealth, social power, safety, harmony, and stability of society, relationships, and self.

The high overall mean of the adolescents' personal and societal values has significant implications for their development, well-being, and role in shaping the future. By placing a strong emphasis on both personal and societal values, adolescents demonstrate a balanced and holistic approach to their growth and engagement with the world around them (Williamson & Mills, 2022). The high level of self-transcendence suggests that adolescents are deeply concerned with the well-being of others and the environment, which can serve as a foundation for empathy, compassion, and a sense of global responsibility (Gustavo & Zevallos, 2024).

While the personal value of self-enhancement received the lowest mean, it is important to note that a moderate emphasis on authority, wealth, social power, safety, harmony, and stability can still play a role in adolescents' personal and social development. These values can provide a sense of structure, motivation, and security as adolescents navigate the challenges of growing up and establishing their place in the world (Schonthaler et al. 2022). However, the lower emphasis on self-enhancement compared to other values may indicate that adolescents are more focused on contributing to greater good and fostering positive relationships than on pursuing individual gain or status (Bilodeau, 2021).

The balance between personal and societal values demonstrated by adolescents in this study can have far-reaching implications for their future roles as leaders, innovators, and change-makers (Karagianni & Montgomery, 2021). By prioritizing self-transcendence and openness to change while also recognizing the importance of conservation, adolescents are well-positioned to address the complex challenges facing our world, such as social inequality, environmental degradation, and rapid technological advancement (Khalid et al. 2023). Their commitment to ensuring the welfare of others and the environment, coupled with their adaptability and respect for tradition, can enable

them to develop innovative solutions and forge collaborative partnerships to drive positive change (Bomelburg & Gassman, 2024).

Moreover, the high level of societal values among adolescents highlights the importance of fostering supportive and inclusive communities that nurture their growth and encourage their active engagement (Thompson et al. 2023). By providing opportunities for adolescents to contribute to the well-being of their groups, societies, and the environment, parents, educators, and community leaders can help them develop a strong sense of purpose, empathy, and social responsibility (Bilodeau, 2021). This, in turn, can lead to the emergence of a generation of compassionate, ethical, and visionary leaders who are committed to building a more just, sustainable, and harmonious world (Murugan, 2020).

To sum, the high levels of personal and societal values exhibited by adolescents in this study underscore their potential to become agents of positive change and shape a brighter future for all (Lemon, 2022). By nurturing and supporting their development, society can harness the power of their values, creativity, and passion to address the pressing challenges of our time and create a more equitable, resilient, and thriving world for generations to come (Faizullina & Karpova, 2024).

The regression analysis presented in Table 2 demonstrates the significant influence of parents' values on their adolescents' values. The results show that the entire model is significant ($F = 10.05$, $p = .000$), with 53.5 percent of the variability in adolescents' personal and societal values being accounted for by a combination of their parents' values. This finding allows for the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that parents who demonstrated a high level of values indeed have a substantial influence on their adolescents who highly manifest their values.

Table 2.
Regression Analysis of the Influence of Parents' Values to their Adolescents' Values in General

PARENTS' VALUES	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	-.134	.832		-.161	.873
Mother's Personal Values	-.604	.276	-.426	-2.19*	.035
Mothers' Societal Values	.963	.348	.587	2.77**	.009
Fathers' Personal Values	.479	.219	.392	2.19*	.035
Fathers' Societal Values	.161	.243	.126	.663	.511

Model Summary

R = .731 R² = .535 Adjusted R² = .481 F = 10.05** p = .000

**significant at 0.01 level *significant at 0.05 level

The regression analysis presented in Table 16 demonstrates the significant influence of parents' values on their adolescents' values. The results show that the entire model is significant ($F = 10.05$, $p = .000$), with 53.5 percent of the variability in adolescents' personal and societal values being accounted for by a combination of their parents' values. This finding allows for the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that parents who demonstrated a high level of values indeed have a substantial influence on their adolescents who highly manifest their values.

The personal values of both fathers ($t=2.19$, $p= .35$) and mothers ($t=2.14$, $p=.035$) significantly influence their adolescents' values. Specifically, the self-enhancement and openness to change values of parents play a crucial role in shaping their adolescents' values. The self-enhancement value of parents encourages their adolescents to establish self-respect, optimize exceptional abilities and capabilities, set clear visions, strive for productivity, and consistently practice creativity (Sedikes et al., 2023). This value provides a foundation for adolescents to develop the skills necessary to lead independent lives. On the other hand, parents' openness to change value motivates adolescents to engage in new, exciting, and engaging activities that lead to a happy, joyful, and satisfying life with harmonious relationships, rather than repeatedly following the same old routines (Hill et al., 2024).

Interestingly, only the mothers' societal values ($t=2.77$, $p=.009$) (self-conservation and self-transcendence) were found to influence their adolescents' values. These values are considered socially acceptable (Barni et al., 2023). Mothers' self-conservation value teaches adolescents to place a high importance on maintaining good health, ensuring family safety, respecting, and obeying the elderly, and showing patriotism to their country. This value fosters solidarity by preserving customs and traditions for both the present and future generations. Additionally, mothers' self-transcendence value emphasizes the importance of living in peace and harmony with others by practicing maximum tolerance, profound understanding, and maintaining open communication in every situation. This value stresses that protecting the well-being of other people is of the utmost priority.

The findings of this study have significant implications for understanding the transmission of values from parents to their adolescent children (Barni et al. 2023). The results highlight the critical role that both fathers and mothers play in shaping their adolescents' personal and societal values (Pramono et al. 2020). By modeling and emphasizing values such as self-enhancement, openness to change, self-transcendence, and conservation, parents can help their adolescents develop a strong sense of self, adaptability, respect for tradition, and concern for others (Pustulka, 2023).

Moreover, the study underscores the unique contribution of mothers in instilling socially acceptable values in their adolescents. This finding suggests that mothers may have a particularly influential role in guiding their children's moral and social development, ensuring that they internalize values that promote social harmony, respect for authority, and concern for the well-being of others (Song et al. 2024).

As parents and educators seek to support the healthy development of adolescents, these findings can inform strategies for fostering positive values and behaviors. By creating home and educational environments that emphasize self-enhancement, openness to change, conservation, and self-transcendence, parents and teachers can help adolescents develop the skills, attitudes, and values necessary to lead fulfilling lives and contribute positively to society.

Conclusions

The results of the study suggest that both mothers' and fathers' personal values (self-enhancement and openness to change) contributed to their adolescents' personal values, while only the mothers' societal values (self-transcendence and self-conservation) influenced their adolescents' societal values.

This study confirms Gordon's (1979) Personality Trait Theory which posited that personal values are individual goals that serve as guiding principles in a person's life, motivating them to determine which values are essential (Hitlin, 2023). This aligns with the findings of Sagiv et al. (2020), which demonstrated that an individual's thoughts and personality are expressed through their personal values. Although everyone possesses values, each person has a unique set of values (Park & Lee, 2024).

This study also confirms Schwartz's Theory of Basic Human Values which stated that mothers and fathers emphasized the importance of inculcating personal values (self-enhancement and openness to change) in their adolescents. Regarding self-enhancement values, they desired their adolescents to practice self-worth, develop their talents, be goal-oriented, productive, and creative (Sedikes et al. 2023). This encourages adolescents to pursue their interests and regulate individual resources that contribute to their success. Additionally, parents wanted their adolescents to uphold a high openness to change value, encouraging them to explore new and exciting experiences rather than engaging in repetitive activities (Hill et al. 2024). This approach leads adolescents to build positive relationships with others.

Furthermore, this study confirms Schwartz's Theory of Basic Human Values that mothers' societal values (self-transcendence and self-conservation) influenced their adolescents' societal values. Societal values are an acceptable set of moral principles established due to diverse cultural beliefs within a society (Schwartz, 2022; Bronfenbrenner, 2004). These values guide individuals to behave appropriately (Schwartz, 2022). Mothers desired their adolescents to acquire high self-transcendence values by establishing positive relationships, practicing good communication, accepting differences and uniqueness of each person, and avoiding disruptions that harm people and properties. This encourages adolescents to live in peace and harmony with other people and nature. Moreover, mothers wanted their adolescents to obtain high self-conservation values by displaying love for their country, respect, and obedience to elders, sustaining family security, and living a healthy life. This advises adolescents to preserve customs and traditions for future generations.

In addition, this study confirms Bronfenbrenner's Ecological System Theory (1979), which postulated that parents' personal and societal values significantly influence their adolescents' values. As adolescents' primary socializers (Schwartz, 1992; Tulviste, 2020; Bronfenbrenner, 2004), parents transmit values that shape their children into responsible individuals (Baumrind & Thompson, 2022). The family is the fundamental element for studying developmental issues, such as the acquisition of values, particularly in adolescents (Epstein & Sanders, 2022).

Overall, this study highlights the significant influence of both mothers' and fathers' personal values on their adolescents' personal values, while emphasizing the unique role of mothers' societal values in shaping their adolescents' societal values. The findings underscore the importance of parents as primary socializers and value transmitters, as well as the central role of the family in adolescent development. By understanding the impact of parental values on adolescents, families and society can work together to foster positive value systems that contribute to the well-being and success of future generations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion above, the following recommendations are thus offered to:

1. the Parents, that they may continue to:
 - 1.1 inculcate the appropriate personal values (self-enhancement and openness to change) and acceptable societal values (self-transcendence and self-conservation) to their adolescents and
 - 1.2 model the same appropriate personal values (self-enhancement and openness to change) and acceptable societal values (self-transcendence and self-conservation) to their adolescents.
2. the adolescents that they may have the capacity to determine the which among their parents' personal values (self-enhancement and openness to change) and societal values (self-transcendence and self-conservation) are necessary.
3. the future researchers that they may consider to duplicate this study by increasing the number of participants to determine whether the mothers' values or fathers' values influence their adolescents' values in terms of personal values or societal values.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In gathering the data, the researcher asked for an Ethical Clearance from Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee (LC-REC). All the research ethical considerations they stipulated were employed in this study. First, a letter of permission to conduct the study was forwarded to the office of the School's Division Superintendent of Cagayan de Oro City. Second, a copy of the approved letter was given to the school head where the study was conducted. Third, the Questionnaire of the Study with an attached Parent Consent Letter and Adolescents' Assent Letter was distributed to the participants. Only

those parents who signed the consent and adolescents who were consented to by their parents were given the questionnaire.

The mother and father completed the questionnaire separately at home. Adolescents answered the questionnaire without the presence of their parents but with the supervision of an adult (researcher). The accomplished questionnaires were gathered, tabulated, and statistically treated. Gathered information through the survey questionnaire was used only for research purposes and was secured from disclosure to unauthorized persons or outside of the research setting.

There were no known risks in the study. However, the participants' identities, personal and confidential information, and all the other data were kept private. This is in adherence to Republic Act No. 10173 or Data Privacy Act of 2012, "An act protecting individual personal information in information and communication systems in the government and the private sector, creating for this purpose a national privacy commission, and for other purposes" (National Privacy Commission, 2012). The participants were aware that they would not receive any compensation since their participation was voluntary. Benefits of the study were also made known to them, such as understanding which among their personal values and societal values as parents best predict their adolescents' values, and aiding adolescents in evaluating the most appropriate personal values and acceptable societal values of their parents. Moreover, the results of the study were made accessible to the participants, educators, and future researchers.

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